

Current Balance	178,771	How do you see the expansion of your business?
Current Savings	24,425	What type of products do you offer?
Current Investments	244,121	How do you see the future of your industry?
Current Loans	75,382	What are your main competitors?
Current Assets	844,179	How do you see the future of your company?
Current Liabilities	177,145	What are your main challenges?
Current Income	45,000	What are your main opportunities?
Current Expenses	447,271	What are your main risks?
Current Profit	10,729	What are your main strengths?
Current Loss	378,542	What are your main weaknesses?
Current Resources	4,567,284	What are your main goals?

Market Strategy

Marketing strategy is a plan to increase sales and achieve advantages over other competitors. It includes short-term and long-term activities of marketing that has to do with the use of advertising, public relations, and other promotional techniques. The objectives will be based on your goals and the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good idea of your sales and marketing activities. Putting your strategy into action is how your plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you what you are going to work with your targets etc.

Information to focus on to increase sales and achieve advantages over other competitors. It includes short-term and long-term activities of marketing that has to do with the use of advertising, public relations, and other promotional techniques. The objectives will be based on your goals and the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good idea of your sales and marketing activities. Putting your strategy into action is how your plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you what you are going to work with your targets etc.

Putting your strategy into action is how your marketing plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you what you are going to work with your targets etc. It may be through networking, advertising etc. Having the perfect timing with your activities will help you saving money and maximizing sales. The marketing plan should be innovative. It should have the details on how your sales are followed up and the activities you doing to develop your offers.

It is a process to allow an organization to focus resources on the greatest opportunities to increase sales and achieve the company's target. Marketing strategy's goal is to increase sales and achieve advantage over other competitors.

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US RATE RISE CHANCES RECEDE AS JOBS GROWTH SLOW

It is a process to allow an organization to focus resources on the greatest opportunities to increase sales and achieve the company's target. Marketing strategy's goal is to increase sales and achieve advantage over other competitors. It includes short-term and long-term activities of marketing that has to do with the analysis of a company's situation and contribute to its objectives. The objectives will be based on how you gain sales by acquiring and keeping customers.

A marketing strategy helps in making good messages with the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good outcome of your sales and marketing activities.

Putting your strategy into action is how your marketing plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you what you are going to work with your targets etc. It may be through networking, advertising etc. Having the perfect timing with your activities will help you saving money and maximizing sales. The marketing plan should be innovative. It should have the details on how your sales are followed up and the activities you doing to develop your offers.

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WORLD BANK'S STOCK AT ALL-TIME HIGH

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THE WORLD IS MESSED UP

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Strong state, weak society

State capacity, economic development
and clientelism in modern Russia

Aleksandr Gurianov²⁷

Abstract

This paper provides a comparative analysis of how highly differentiated regions of Russia perform in terms of economic development, public services delivery and overall quality of governance while linking these factors to levels of political support for the current incumbent during the latest presidential electoral campaign in 2018.

It introduces the subnational Good Governance Rank to facilitate comparison of distinct regions on a comparable basis.

Additionally, author studies the “economy-state-clientelism” triangle in the modern Russian setting to confirm previous findings from Mexico, Argentina, Cambodia, Germany, United Kingdom and other countries to reveal the typical behavior pattern: politicians favor the poor (because its cheap), citizens favor stalemate (because change is risky) and clientelism coerces and buys (because it’s a time-tested mechanism).

Keywords: Russia, Elections, State capacity, Clientelism, Governance

²⁷ Aleksandr Gurianov is an EMPA 2022 graduate at the Hertie School of Governance in Berlin. The present paper is a shortened version of his MA dissertation.

1. Introduction

Scholars give much attention to studying concepts of state capacity, economic development and clientelism. They select proxies to measure strength of a state, discover how economic environment affects political choice of voters.

A large body of scholarly literature does this on a cross-national level, attempting to reveal similar patterns which may in principle explain socio-political processes in any country. While this approach contributes a lot to political science, we attempt to discover new academic insights on a subnational level of a single country. Russia is way too far away from being homogenous in terms of economic levels and public services provision across its diverse constituencies.

The country provides an interesting research case because no matter cross-regional differences, longevity of single political regime in post-soviet Russia has become its national feature. How is it possible for the biggest country in the world, facing a lot of economic and social issues, to sustain political stability across various regional settings, from frontiers to central cities, from subsidy-intensive to wealthiest constituencies? In this paper we apply insights from scholarly literature across the globe to testbed their findings in the Russian setting, an area which so far has remained understudied. We attempt to clarify how clientelism, represented by vote-buying and coercion, economic and state capacity factors shaped political behavior of voters during presidential elections campaign of 2018.

Section 1 provides theoretical findings from scholarly literature on clientelism and its nature, prerequisites of uneven economic development as well as researchers' views on measuring state capacity. In this section we attempt to pick relevant variables, proxies and indicators that might be available on subnational level in the Russian setting.

Section 2 offers a descriptive analysis of socio-economic and political environment across 83 regions of Russia. By studying highly differentiated regions we attempt to identify similarities in voting patterns to understand how economic wealth and strength of local state influences voter's choice. Additionally, we introduce the Subnational Good Governance Rank, a synthesized index that comprises 6 economic and 5 state capacity indicators to measure overall state performance in each of 83 regions.

Section 3 operates with economic and state capacity variables to explain their relationship to political outcomes in regions of Russia. Here OLS regression analysis is performed to clarify which variables in principle remain robust and explain variation in level of political support for the incumbent. In addition to this, we test 2 hypotheses that address clientelism and coercion during elections. Firstly, we study how federal subsidies influence support for the president by introducing dummy-variable for level of subsidies and controlling for economic and state capacity parameters. Secondly, we introduce dummy variable for "sultanate states" in order to control for coercion in regions that systematically present statistical anomalies for election results.

2. Subnational development: where differences come from

Significant disparity in levels of governance, capacity and economic development on subnational level is widely prevalent globally. It is a popular research subject for a large body of scholarly literature that studies its prerequisites and consequences.

In this paper we clarify the popular “chicken or egg” paradox: is it poor economy and weak state that trigger vote-buying and coercion or is it predominant clientelism that undermines every effort to boost economic growth and programmatic reforms to ensure fair and transparent redistribution?

To answer this question, in this section we shall investigate theoretical aspects of state performance reflected through state capacity, economic development and clientelism.

2.1. Prerequisites of uneven regional development

While working on various aspects of intra-state governance, scholars mostly concentrate on a single aspect, occasionally linking them to other governance-related concepts such as electoral preferences (Putterman&Bockstette 2002) and clientelism. One such paper by Andrienko&Guriev (2004) examines migration patterns in Russia.

While providing important insights about consequences of demographic crisis which unfolded in post-soviet Russia, it indicates prerequisites that triggered economic disparities across regions. Specifically, it says that “during tsarist and soviet times many settlements were created in places where they never would have been located under a market economy”, implying that misallocation of capital and human resources took place which led to difficulties for future generations of government executives.

Authors suggest that Russia governed a non-rational spatial allocation and became “economically colder”, contrary to more rational market economy that reallocates production to warmer regions. Chanda et al. (2002) adds state antiquity to the list of reasons. Authors argue that it is strongly associated with institutional quality and political stability in the cross-country analysis. This approach, however, may not be applicable to study intra-state difference in the Russian setting. Regions of Russia shared the same historical journey (they belonged to USSR and became the part of Russia after it collapsed).

Further elaborating on causes for disparity, Foa&Nistotskaya (2016) introduced the concept of “frontier regions” – constituencies with average to little population density far away from a country’s economic and political center.

To explain significant variations in levels of development and state capacity as compared to non-frontier areas (frontier effect), they pick factors such as ethnolinguistic diversity, socioeconomic modernization and legacies of direct or indirect rule. Although neither of these factors alone may create a weak state setting, predominant perception of distant central rule and its weaker influence over local processes trigger local populations to favor populism, develop individualistic rather than “common good” mindset and vote for libertarian political parties. In addition to these factors, Zhuravskaya&Alesina (2008) imply that linguistically and ethnically segregated countries have a lower quality of government. This may also hold true for regional settings within a single country when it houses many ethno-linguistic groups that choose to form gated communities with limited connection to outsiders.

While all the factors above may impact regional development, we need to apply proxies and indicators that will assist us in measuring degree of such influence. Scholars suggest various parameters for this purpose. Bergman&Feser (2017) emphasize the importance of heightened trade relations, which create “new economic geography” paradigm where regions and their local industries, other than whole countries, contribute most to international trade which allows us to consider proportion of exports in local gross regional product (GRP). Moroshkina (2018) studied cross-regional differences and disparities in Russia by GRP per capita in current and constant prices to account for inflation. Al-Hussaini et al. (2021) study development in the city of Samarra, Iraq using UN-Habitat’s principles, including economic policies presented by employment rate and R’nD expenditure. Ryazantsev&Khramova (2018) considered push-factors that facilitated out-migration from Russian regions elsewhere by using real income per capita, access to housing and unemployment.

2.2. Measuring state capacity

State capacity is a broad term. Depending on how we answer the question “the capacity to do what?” (Hanson&Singman 2020), state capacity may mean many things. Firstly, it may be a part of an even broader term of governance that the World Bank defines as “the traditions and institutions by which authority in a country is exercised”. This definition covers 3 components: process of government selection, monitoring and replacement; government capacity to formulate and implement sound policies; citizens’ support of public institutions “that govern social and economic interactions”.²⁸

Secondly, it may carry a Weberian meaning of “the organizational and bureaucratic ability to implement governing projects” which includes merit-based human resources management that trains and hires well-trained professionals, presence of state and its ability to efficiently extract resources (Zhang 2021). Finally, state capacity may be about infrastructural and despotic power which may be defined as “the range of actions which state elite is empowered to make without routine consultation with civil society groups”. According to Mann (1984), here state capacity is defined through core functions: maintenance of internal order, military/defense aggression, maintenance of communication infrastructure and economic redistribution.

²⁸ World Bank. (n.d.). Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) Project: <http://info.worldbank.org/governance/WGI/>

No matter the preferred definition, measuring state capacity poses significant challenges. To start with, “national level trends may not reflect distinctive developments at the subnational or regional level” for some countries “exhibit a high degree of heterogeneity” (Svoia&Sen 2012). Because of this, international indices and rankings such as Quality of Governance (QoG), State Capacity Index (HSI), Government Effectiveness (WGI), State Fragility Index (SFI), Failed States Index (FSI), Impartial Public Administration (VDEM) or Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) cannot be used as proper assessment benchmarks. Then, “measures of state capacity are strongly related among each other and capture one-dimensional concept of state capacity” (Vaccaro 2020) which may trigger numerous problems for statistical analysis such as multicollinearity (Ryazantsev&Khramova 2018), omitted variable bias and reverse causality (Acemoglu, Johnson, and Robinson 2001). In addition, there is yet no scholar consensus on proper measurement of state capacity because “it is not always distinct from other concepts of interest such as economic development or regime type” as well as lack of geographic and temporal coverage for data in this domain (Hanson&Sigman 2020).

Despite these obstacles, scholars attempted to identify variables that may serve as proxies for state capacity in the large number of parameters that assess bureaucratic, administrative, legal, infrastructural, fiscal and military capacity. Hanson and Sigman (2020) conducted cross-national study where they employed a set of 21 indicators that measure administrative capacity (children enrolled in schools, infant mortality rate, literacy rate), coercive capacity (military expenditures and personnel) and extractive capacity (tax revenue as share of GDP, taxes on income and trade).

However, due to noisiness and interconnectedness of data the results were mixed, suggesting that military-related indicators have the least correlation with state capacity. La Porta et al. (1999) discovered that state capacity is strongly influenced by historical circumstances such as legal origins, ethno-linguistic heterogeneity, economic factors (Gross National Product per capita), public goods provision (infant mortality rate, literacy rate, quality of infrastructure) as well as government size (transfers and subsidies as share of GDP, government consumption). Authors suggest that “poorly performing governments are smaller and collect fewer taxes”. Setiono&Levchenko (2018) tested influence of foreign direct investments and exports on state’s fiscal capacity (tax-to-GDP ratio) in a cross-national study. Bustikova (2017) discovered that infant mortality rate serves as a good proxy to measure “historical competence of states”.

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Photo by [refargotohp](https://www.refargotohp.com).

2.3. Nature, forms and symptoms of clientelism

As consensus on the proper definition of clientelism does not exist, scholars provide a range of interpretations for this multifaceted phenomenon. In a large body of literature clientelism is defined as a patron-client relationship where distribution of rewards takes place in exchange for vote choices (Kramon 2018, Nichter 2014). Its key features cover power asymmetry and hierarchy, discretionary distribution of resources, iteration and contingency (Hicken 2011). This definition, however, is not exhaustive for it does not fully consider the power asymmetry factor.

The state's power may be defined as the power over members of society to the extent where state can get members of society do something that members of society would not otherwise do (Lindvall&Teorell 2016). If this is true, and the state has power to suppress actions and intentions of its citizens, then the latter would inevitably be subject to coercion as an alternative to material rewards if they do not oblige with what the state wants. Therefore, in the clientelism domain state's toolkit will include not only economic incentives and material benefits ("carrots") but also coercive actions ("sticks"). Coming from this perspective we agree with definition of clientelism provided by Hilgers (2012). According to author, clientelism is an exchange in which individuals maximize their interests... involves longevity, diffuseness...and inequality". However, it does not always entail face-to-face contact because clientelism may be of impersonal nature, introducing political brokerage as intermediary between state's intentions and individual's political choice.

Emergence of clientelism is strongly dependent on economic and state capacity factors. In the context of state with weak reputation, both demand and supply sides work in favor of clientelism. On the one hand, here "voters... do not find party platforms based on public goods provision credible" (Bustikova 2017). On the other hand, "politicians are unable to credibly commit to delivering campaign promises" (Keefer&Vlaicu 2007). Such a setting creates favorable conditions for emergence of clientelism: skeptical about administrative performance of their state, citizens often choose to turn to politicians they know and trust. In the context of poor economic conditions, the situation repeats itself. Poor voters "favor upfront, targeted benefits over broad future policy changes" whereas politicians are happy to target such voters for they "cannot credibly commit to delivering the policies that more prosperous voters want" (Nathan 2016). In other words, the law of diminishing returns works in client-patron relationship. The higher the voter's income is, the more costly it is to buy their vote (Hicken 2011). Therefore, it may not be in the interest of a government to improve quality of life and stimulate economic development because voters' expectations and demands will rise, forcing the state to splurge on costly programmatic incentives. Evidence from Hungary sums up this as the "poor versus poor" conflict which depicts polar views on clientelism (critics versus supporters) which depends on belonging to social policy transfers group or being excluded from it (Mares&Young 2019). Less is clear about the size of public sector. On the one hand, Kitschelt&Wilkinson found out that clientelism is associated with larger state. Contrary to that, La Porta et al. (1999) discovered that strong positive correlation between public sector size and state capacity.

No matter the differences, we extract valuable insights from scholarly literature that the poor, contrary to popular belief, are unlikely to vote in favor of higher redistribution and programmatic parties because they are skeptical about their ability to transform status quo. This paradigm links together economic, capacity and clientelism factors that shape political landscapes worldwide. No matter the country context, voters face “pocketbook versus sociotropic” dilemma (Kinder&Kiewiet 1981) that forces them to choose between individual (pocketbook) and common good (sociotropic) interests.

The results of field experiment in Benin showed that African voters “invariably have a much stronger preference for private transfers than for public goods or projects of national interest” (Wantchekon 2003). Arslantas (2019) conducted study in Istanbul to reveal that clientelism effectively targeted the poorest voters who supported neoliberal policies of the ruling AKP party although such policies undermined well-being of this voter group. Furthermore, significant inequality made Indonesia the 3rd country in the world “as a country that has the most money politics” which made vote-buying a full-scale nationwide practice (Habibi 2021). A study by Nadraliev (2021) showed how the ruling party in Kyrgyz Republic ensured favorable results by coercing students in state-controlled universities, contrary to private schools where opposition took over. Mares&Young (2019) labeled economic coercion as “one of the oldest non-programmatic electoral strategies” which was witnessed in Germany (wage decrease and post-electoral harassment by supervisors for supporting opposition), United Kingdom (hiring practices based on political allegiance).

Filipovich et al. (2021) discovered coercion in rural Mexico where local cash-transfer programmes were used to direct voters’ political choice in favor of the current incumbent. Evidence from Cambodia revealed hundreds of thousands of cases of land dispossession from private owners for supporting the “wrong” party (Loughlin 2020). Finally, in the case of Russia, Yoshiko (2004) found political synchronization between the rich and the poor regions that, despite their differences, did not seek greater autonomy from the central government after the USSR dissolved.

Source: unsplash.com.
Photo by Mike Kononov.

3. Methodology

Being a home to more than 190 nationalities and every major religion, Russia provides unparalleled political consistency in choosing its single course of political leadership despite internal economic disparities and significant variations in quality of public services and life in general.

During presidential elections of 2018 every region voted in support of the current incumbent Vladimir Putin. The political campaign was not different from previous elections, both presidential and parliamentary, and envisaged results of national elections in 2020 that supported constitutional amendments to allow current president to stay in power until 2036. Is it the case of exceptional governance and strong charismatic politicians? Or is there a room for clientelism and coercion? The latter comprises research question. In order to answer it we plan to explain variation across voting preferences at regional level by state capacity and economic development.

3.1. Data and variables operationalization

Studying developments on subnational level is a complicated task. Majority of international indices and records assess entire countries other than their constituencies. From these global rankings we learn how Russia in principle performs in terms of Doing Business (Rank 28/190 in 2020²⁹), Transparency (Rank 136/180 in 2021³⁰) and T-index (14.5 in 2021³¹), Public Integrity (6.72 in 2020³²), Global Competitiveness (Rank 38/137 in 2018³³) and many others. However, by presenting a bigger picture, these rankings do not reveal internal undergoing economic and social processes as well as intrastate quality of decision-making that eventually affects quality of life. Identifying subnational differences is crucial to understanding how varying levels of economic development and state capacity affect political behavior of citizens across distinct regional settings. In our framework we study 83 out of 85 regions of Russia. We do not include 2 regions which are the city of Sevastopol and Crimea. The federal government has been investing considerable resources in both territories to drop off Ukrainian heritage of economic underdevelopment and to rush a success story under the Russian command. Their exclusion helps us to reduce potential noise coming from systematic targeted government interventions in these 2 regions.

²⁹ World Bank. (n.d.). Doing Business 2020 – Russian Federation
<https://russian.doingbusiness.org/content/dam/doingBusiness/country/r/russia/RUS.pdf>

³⁰ Transparency International. (n.d.). Country Data – Russian Federation
<https://www.transparency.org/en/countries/russia>

³¹ Corruption Risk Forecast. (n.d.). Transparency in Russian Federation
<http://www.corruptionrisk.org/country/?country=RUS#transparency>

³² Corruption Risk Forecast. (n.d.). Index of Public Integrity in Russian Federation
<http://www.corruptionrisk.org/country/?country=RUS#integrity>

³³ World Economic Forum. (n.d.). The Global Competitiveness Index – Russian Federation
https://www3.weforum.org/docs/GCR2017-2018/03CountryProfiles/Standalone2-pagerprofiles/WEF_GCI_2017_2018_Profile_Russian_Federation.pdf

We compare regions of Russia based on 13 indicators. Our dependent variable (Y) is % of support for the current incumbent during presidential elections of 2018. Independent variables include 6 parameters for economic development and 5 state capacity proxies. Independent variables that measure economic development include logarithm of Gross Regional Product in 2018 (X1), logarithm of Average Income per Capita (X2), Manufacturing Output (X3), R'n'D Expenses (X4), Unemployment Rate (X5) and logarithm of Total Taxes paid (X6). Independent variables that represent proxies of state capacity are Infant Mortality Rate (IMR, X7), Net Migration Rate (X8), Exports-to-GRP ratio (X9), Value of Cargo Transported (X10) and Number of Hospital Beds (X11).

Clientelism variable is presented by value of Federal Subsidy Transfers (X12). Electoral Turnout provides us with proxy for coercion (X13). For research purposes we pick official statistical data published by the Federal State Statistics Service (Rosstat) for variables representing state capacity and economic development; informational agency RosBiznesConsulting (RBC) for election results and coercion dummy-variable; the National Budget Information Portal (budget.gov.ru) for the level of federal subsidy transfers to regions of Russia. Variables represented in national currency (RUR) are converted into European currency using the average annual RUR/EUR exchange rate for 2018. **Annex A** provides information about variables and links to respective sources as well as datasets used for this research.

3.2. Good governance ranking

Assessment of diverse and differentiated constituencies is challenged by multidimensional nature of proxies. The 'medical' set of proxies, such as IMR and number of hospital beds, despite serving the goal of measuring state capacity, additionally captures population size which distorts our estimations of state capacity. 'Economic' proxies including taxes collected and exports-to-gdp may compromise external validity simply because some regions have manufacturing or mining specialization while others don't. 'Infrastructural' proxy is affected by geography of regions.

For example, constituencies outside of Trans-Siberian Route are unable to compete in terms of cargo transportation with those connected to this international logistics chain. As a result, our preliminary analysis provides mixed results which do not explicitly reveal the best and the worst performers on subnational level.

However, they serve good purpose for comparison with a group of economic indicators. Putting together economic and state capacity proxies allows us to capture holistic overview of regions than just by looking at individual proxies and reveal certain trends in how they grow and perform. We begin by calculating separate arithmetic means of economic development indicators and state capacity proxies to introduce 2 synthesized scores (Economic Score and State Capacity Score).

To better account for drastic differences between regions with distinct features and conditions we come up with the Subnational Governance Rank which is calculated as an arithmetic mean of Economic and State Capacity scores (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Subnational Good Governance Rank 2018 (15 regions)

Rank	Region	Total Score (100 – best)	Economic Score	State Capacity Score
1	Saint-Petersburg	87,7	95,5	79,8
2	Moscow	83,0	98,5	67,4
3	Tuymen	82,9	91,8	74
4	Moscow region	82,4	95,2	69,6
5	Tatarstan	81,9	90,8	73
...	...	...	...	...
74	Tyva	37,4	20,5	54,2
75	Dagestan	37,2	43,2	31,2
76	North Ossetia -Alania	36,7	27,5	45,8
77	Jewish autonomous region	35,9	26,5	45,2
78	Kurgan region	34,9	31,5	38,2
79	Kabardian-Balkar Republic	31,7	27,5	35,8
80	Chechen Republic	30,1	26,5	33,6
81	Ingushetia	27,6	18,3	36,8
82	Karachaev-Circassian Republic	26,1	24,0	28,2
83	Kalmykia	23,6	21,2	26

Table above is a 15-region sample of the full Good Governance Rank for the Russian regions (see [Annex B](#) for the full Rank) that provides a holistic overview of best and worst regions in terms of economic development and state capacity. Overall, our methodology allows us to better align significantly differentiated regional settings and come up with their proper cross-regional assessment.

This rank is coherent with our previous findings that suggest strong connection between state capacity and regional economic development. Where public services delivery is high, economy is in principle stronger. Same relationship applies to under-performing constituencies. [Table 2](#) adds regional election data in 2018 to compare political allegiance with governance scores. In principle, regions with the highest support for the incumbent are among the ones with poorest scores in our ranking. Contrary to that, governance leaders provide less political support during elections.

Table 2: Subnational Good Governance Rank 2018 and Election Outcomes (15 regions)

Rank	Region	% for the Incumbent	Total Score (100 – best)	Economic Score	State Capacity Score
1	Saint-Petersburg	75,01	87,7	95,5	79,8
2	Moscow	70,88	83,0	98,5	67,4
3	Tuymen	79,75	82,9	91,8	74
4	Moscow region	74,49	82,4	95,2	69,6
5	Tatarstan	82,09	81,9	90,8	73
...	...	...	...	...	...
74	Tyva	91,98	37,4	20,5	54,2
75	Dagestan	90,77	37,2	43,2	31,2
76	North Ossetia -Alania	81,51	36,7	27,5	45,8
77	Jewish autonomous region	67,48	35,9	26,5	45,2
78	Kurgan region	73,3	34,9	31,5	38,2
79	Kabardian-Balkar Republic	93,38	31,7	27,5	35,8
80	Chechen Republic	91,44	30,1	26,5	33,6
81	Ingushetia	83,17	27,6	18,3	36,8
82	Karachaev-Circassian Republic	87,64	26,1	24,0	28,2
83	Kalmykia	81,66	23,6	21,2	26

Source: unsplash.com.
Photo by Alex Zarubi.

4. Hypotheses tests and results

Our data depicts a puzzling governance landscape across Russian regions. Firstly, high economic wealth does not automatically imply strong political support for the regime. Secondly, poor state capacity may contradict common sense and go along with Russia's highest allegiance with incumbent politicians during election campaigns.

Why wealthy Tatarstan and poor Chechnya demonstrate unparalleled political support despite differences in state capacity? Why 2 governance leaders, Moscow and Saint-Petersburg, are among regions with the least political support?

Given such distinct differences we assume that election outcomes may be subject to clientelism in the form of “sticks” and “carrots”, representing coercion and material rewards, respectively. Such assumption goes in line with what scholars call an investment dilemma (Persson 2011) of choosing between “pursuing immediate policy goals or investing in future capacity”.

In the case of Russia, there is a high probability for decision-makers to choose the former option due to limited of resources and administrative constraints. This corresponds well with Calvo&Murillo (2019) who emphasize the high relevance of the law of diminishing returns for policymakers. It is much cheaper to buy votes from low-income voters than from high-income voters, and as we have previously seen, cross-regional economic wealth is highly dispersed, providing hospitable environment for such interventions. Based on our findings, we formulate 2 research hypotheses:

H1: Votes are bought by incumbent central government (clientelism hypothesis)

H2: Votes are coerced by incumbent central government (extortion hypothesis)

4.1. Model specifications

We perform ordinary least squares (OLS) regression analysis to test how level of political support changes depending on a set of independent variables that represent levels of state capacity and economic development. On the one hand, every voter is on the receiving side of economic policies that affect their purchasing power and household economic wealth. On the other hand, they are also subject to governance decisions in healthcare, infrastructure and development made by local authorities which affect overall quality of life in each regional setting. As our models include a total of 12 independent variables, we conduct multicollinearity tests to eliminate this potential effect by building correlation matrices and identifying pair correlations with coefficient of 0.7 or more.

For models containing economic variables (X1-X6) we identified multicollinearity for 2 pairs: X1 (Gross Regional Product) – X6 (Federal Taxes Paid) and X3 (Manufacturing Output) – X4 (R'n'D Expenses). For models with state capacity proxies we did not find any signs of multicollinearity. For joint model (Model 3) there was no multicollinearity between 2 groups of variables.

Model 1 studies relationship between election outcomes (Y) and economic factors (X1-X6) in the sample of 83 regions. This model provides single statistically significant coefficient for unemployment variable (at the 0.01 level). It suggests that a 1% increase in unemployment would result in a 0.5% increase in political support for the current incumbent, controlling for Gross Regional Product (GRP), Average Income per Capita, Manufacturing output, R'n'D, and Federal Taxes paid and holding them constant. It may be surprising that higher unemployment positively affects election outcomes, yet it corresponds well with findings by Chen (2018) who provides empirical evidence of such pattern in which the poor in a weak state setting tend to demand less redistribution, for they expect “no benefit from alternative political parties” and expect redistribution of any kind through established patron-client connections.

Model 2 further elaborates on Chen’s findings to reveal relation between political outcome (Y) and state capacity (X7-X11) for 83 regions. This model provides 2 statistically significant coefficients for infant mortality rate and hospital beds, both at the 0.05 level. First coefficient suggests that a 1% increase in infant mortality rate would result in 1.14% increase in electoral preference for incumbent. Second coefficient suggests that 1 unit increase in hospital beds would reduce election outcome by 0.19%. Both are in line with previous findings, depicting negative relation between state capacity and electoral support.

Model 3 investigates how economic variables (X2, X5) and state capacity proxies (X7, X11) simultaneously impact level of electoral support (Y) in a full sample of 83 regions in 2018. While controlling for state capacity variables, economic factors (unemployment) are no longer statistically significant. This model suggests pattern similar to the previous model, with infant mortality rate and number of hospital beds being statistically significant at the 0.05 level and depicting an inverse relationship between levels of state power and elections outcome. The next set of models deals with a smaller sample. Given significant variation in economic development and state capacity we removed several outliers from the initial sample of 83 regions. Based on the Good Governance Rank introduced in Section 2, we removed 10 outliers, including top 5 and bottom 5 regions with the highest and lowest total score, respectively. They are Saint-Petersburg, City of Moscow, Tuymen, Moscow region, Tatarstan and Kalmykia, Karachaev-Circassian Republic, Ingushetia, Chechen Republic, Kabardian-Balkar Republic. Here we repeat the procedure for the new sample of 73 regions, reducing the number of independent variables to 4.

Model 4 investigates impact of state capacity proxies (X7, X11) on election outcomes (Y) in the same sample of 73 regions. It partly corresponds with regression results in Model 2. Coefficient for the number of hospital beds is statistically significant at the 0.05 level and suggests negative relation between state capacity and electoral support for the incumbent.

Model 5 studies relationship between election outcomes (Y) and economic parameters (X2, X5) while controlling for state capacity proxies (X7, X11) in the 73-region sample. It goes in line with previous models, providing statistically significant coefficient for the number of hospital beds and its inverse relation to electoral support for the incumbent.

Table 3: Regression Outputs for Models 1-5

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>				
	% of votes for the incumbent in 2018				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Gross Regional Product (log function)	1.59 (14.71)				
Average Income per Capita (log function)	-5.53 (5.42)		-1.62 (4.59)		0.87 (3.78)
Industrial / Mining Output (mln EUR)	-1.05 (0.00)				
R'n'D Expenitures (mln EUR)	-0.0003 (0.0024)				
Unemployment Rate (%)	0.52*** (0.24)		0.26 (0.21)		-0.06 (0.18)
Amount of Federal Taxes Paid (log function)	-0.18 (2.10)				
Infant Mortality Rate (%)		114.2** (42.7)	98.7** (43.4)	39.4 (37.4)	43.5 (39.1)
Migration Rate (% of population)		0.0005 (0.01)			
Export to GDP ratio (%)		-3.97 (3.72)			
Cargo Transportation by Roads (mln tonnes)		0.002 (0.02)			
Hospital Beds (Number per 10 000 population)		-0.19** (0.05)	-0.17** (0.05)	-0.12** (0.04)	-0.13** (0.04)
Y-intercept	86.6** (14.7)	87.2** (4.4)	88.5** (12.4)	84.3** (3.3)	82.7** (10.3)
Observations	83	83	83	73	73
R ²	0.11	0.22	0.23	0.10	0.11

Notes: **p<0.05; ***p<0.01. Standard error in brackets

Table 3 provides regression outputs for Models 1-5. Results of our analyses suggest that most independent variables that we picked are unlikely to predict election outcomes on subnational level in Russia. At the same time, state capacity proxies seem to better explain variation in electoral support as R2 for Model 2 that studies relation between dependent variable and state capacity variables is higher than for Models 1 which studies isolated impact of economic variables. Additionally, infant mortality rate and number of hospital beds both remain statistically significant (except for IMR in Models 4-5). Finally, 2 economic variables, logIncome and unemployment, may be relevant for further research as factors which may influence voter's behavior. Both correspond with empirical findings by scholars that highlight negative relationship between economic factors and political outcomes.

4.2. Clientelism hypothesis

Model 6 investigates impact of federal subsidies (X12) on election results (Y) in the sample of 83 regions. For the purposes of this study, we do not pick value of federal subsidies transferred to the regional budgets. Using quantitative data may trigger an outlier problem, given significant variation in federal transfer amounts across regions. Every region in Russia is labelled between 4 subsidy groups (1 – no subsidies, 2 – subsidized up to 10%, 3 – subsidized by 10-40%, 4 – heavily subsidized by more than 40%). Therefore, we introduce dummy variable which helps to account for variation in subsidy values and eliminate outlier issue represented by regions with extremely high federal transfers or no subsidies at all. Regression in this model provides interesting results. The coefficient for dummy variable representing subsidy-intensive regions (>40%) is statistically significant at the level of 0.05 with positive impact on electoral support for the incumbent. It suggests that in such regions on average electoral support is 6.9% higher than in regions with no federal subsidies. As for other subsidy groups, those constituencies receiving 10-40% of regional budgets in transfers, also demonstrate higher political support. Election outcomes are 0.67% more favorable for the incumbent than in regions without transfers. Interestingly, regions which receive up to 10% transfers, record lower political support which is 1.25% lower than in regions which receive no subsidies. Partial explanation may come from comparably mild impact of subsidies on voter's choice without substantially affecting their quality of life which in general is less than in generally wealthier subsidy-free constituencies.

Model 7 controls subsidy levels for 4 independent variables representing economic development and state capacity. This model confirms our previous findings of inverse relationship between state capacity and political support. Both coefficients of infant mortality rate and number of hospital beds variables are statistically significant at the level of 0.05. Additionally, the model supports the idea of clientelism that influences voters' behavior in the weak state setting much more than economic variables. The coefficient signs for dummy variables match those from previous models, in principle suggesting that subsidy-intensive (and respectively less prominent in delivering policies successfully) regions are more supportive of political regime. There, political support for the incumbent is 2.6% higher than in constituencies that receive no subsidies at all.

Table 4: Regression Outputs for Models 6-7

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>	
	% of votes for the incumbent in 2018	
	(6)	(7)
Regions with subsidies less than 10%	-1.25 (1.93)	-1.38 (2.36)
Regions with subsidies at 10-40%	0.67 (2.0)	0.31 (2.64)
Regions with subsidies more than 40%	6.93** (2.94)	2.66 (3.8)
Average Income per Capita (log function)		-2.78 (5.85)
Unemployment Rate (%)		0.11 (0.24)
Infant Mortality Rate (%)		88.88** (44.51)
Hospital Beds (Number per 10 000 population)		-0.16** (0.05)
Y-intercept	75.97** (1.65)	92.45** (15.4)
Observations	83	83
R ²	0.11	0.26

Notes: ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$. Standard error in brackets

Table 4 sums up regression outputs for Models 7 and 8. While controlling for income, unemployment, infant mortality and hospital beds, we retain directions of coefficients that we identified in initial Model (7). Although regression results do not explicitly reveal the degree to which federal subsidies influence voters' political choice, we witness a clear voting pattern. Despite economic constraints and low quality of public services, as presented by state capacity proxies, individuals cast their votes in favor of the current incumbent in underdeveloped regional settings. Out of 8 regions which receive the highest subsidy transfers, 5 are constituencies at the bottom of the good governance rank. They are Kalmykia (rank 83), Ingushetia (#81), Chechen Republic (#80), Dagestan (#75) and Republic of Tyva (#74). 2 more are Crimea and Sevastopol which are behind the scope of the study. The highest-ranking in this group is Republic of Altai (#53). On the one hand, it may be exclusively a matter of "no alternative" mindset, which, as scholars suggest, may emerge in weak state setting and push poor voters against any political change for it is unlikely to change status quo. On the other hand, federal transfers could serve as a form of administrative and political control over constituencies. Whereas the central government is concerned to ensure visibility of democratic election process while producing favorable results for itself, the regional governments, especially in underdeveloped settings, are dependent on federal subsidies. This altogether creates a room for mutually beneficial clientelist transactions on *federal-regional* rather than on *individual-regional* level where a voter would engage in transaction with the representative of local bureaucracy.

While this holds true for subsidy-intensive regions, we assume that the clientelist exchange is less clear in different parts of Russia. Regions that receive federal funds on a smaller scale, as well tend to provide favorable political outcomes for the incumbent, but at a milder degree than heavily subsidized constituencies. The second group of 28 regions that receive 10-40% in federal subsidies is diverse. On the one hand it contains several prominent constituencies which are way above the average governance score, including Saratov (#34), Penza (#36) and Bryansk (#42) regions. On the other hand, they co-exist with Kalmykia (#83), Karachaev-Circassian Republic (#82) and Kabardian-Balkar Republic (#79). Coefficient interpretation for this group is less obvious due to disparities in levels of economic activity and quality of public services. The degree to which clientelism influences political choice is blurred due to diverse nature of this group of regions. We may only assume that at least some regions, such as ones belonging to the North Caucasus Federal District, are subject to regional-federal clientelist exchange because they share the same economic and administrative traits as their heavily subsidized neighbors. However, we should also stress that clientelist transaction should be less visible and less impactful in more prominent regions which have better-than-average scores.

The third group of 35 regions that are funded up to 10% from federal government is more homogenous than the previous one in terms of governance scores. Here, only 10 regions such as Chelyabinsk (#73), Khakassia (#65), Astrakhan (#64), Omsk (#55) and Smolensk (#49) fall below the average score. Overall, election outcomes in this group are opposite to the previous 2 groups. As our last 2 models suggested, there is a negative relation between subsidies and political preferences.

These 35 regions, however, despite predominantly belonging to below-the-average group, receive smallest federal subsidies while having worse economic conditions than the base group of regions that do not receive any subsidies.

Therefore, we may conclude that such “political negativity” may be subject to dissatisfaction with overall governance coupled with little financial contributions from the federal government. This group of regions is important for our research because it reveals how dramatic reduction of federal subsidies, as compared to subsidized regions, may affect electoral behavior. Firstly, it highlights the existing clientelism in constituencies which are less developed and more funded. Secondly, it highlights voters’ response to poor governance in the context of little to no federal transfers.

To conclude, we revealed a clear voting pattern across highly differentiated groups of Russian regions. Their comparison showed that clientelism is an important tool in the hands of the central government. Climbing up the governance rank and comparing election behavior we clearly witness how voters respond to poor state capacity and weak regional economies depending on the level of federal funding. At the same time, it is unlikely to be a direct clientelist exchange between voters and officials. Rather, we may be witnessing federal-regional clientelist transactions aimed to reach mutually beneficial goals for central and regional bureaucrats. However, what remains an open question is why individual voters, while not receiving any benefits from casting their votes in favor of the incumbent, still attend election campaigns and ensure election outcomes favorable for the incumbent.

4.3. Coercion hypothesis

To answer the question of why individual voters keep on supporting the existing government despite drastic differences in economic wealth and quality of public services, we test the coercion hypothesis. Normally scholars apply qualitative research techniques via surveys or mass media analysis (Yoshiko 2004) while studying social behavior. However, for the purposes of our research and in the absence of any systematized data on acts of coercion during political campaigns we turn to measuring levels of coercion through the electoral turnout proxy.

In Russia, electoral turnout is a “convincing benchmark of election legitimacy” as representatives of the ruling party, United Russia, say³⁴. Additionally, such information is available on subnational level. We therefore investigate influence of electoral turnout on levels of political support while additionally controlling for 4 independent variables which we used earlier.

Model 8 studies relationship between election outcomes (Y) and electoral turnout (X13) for the sample of 83 regions during election campaign 2018. Regression output provides a statistically significant coefficient for the independent variable at the level of 0.05 highlighting positive relation with voters’ support for the incumbent. While not controlling for other independent variables, a 1% increase in turnout would boost incumbent’s political support by 0.5%. This model does not explicitly reveal facts of coercion, as voters may be only expressing their political commitment to the regime. However, it is still puzzling how patriotic local populations are in the regions with the highest subsidy transfers and poorest governance.

Additionally, it is surprising how the highest political support is coupled with the highest election turnout. This may imply supervised visits of individuals to the polling stations and control of casting an appropriate vote at the risk of losing jobs or having administrative difficulties. At the very least, such facts were revealed in Khabarovsk where military personnel and their families were coerced to attend the elections in 2016. 2 years before that, it was found out that 39.8% of voters in Saint-Petersburg were military conscripts and contract servicemen serving their term in the city but not living there.³⁵ As for 2018, this election year registered new cases of coercion, enforcement from local elites in lieu of independent electoral observation. That year Russian media introduced a term of “electoral sultanates” – regions which vote according to their own rules and produce statistically abnormal records of political support and electoral turnout.³⁶ All these facts, however, do not explicitly answer if our models prove facts of coercion.

³⁴ United Russia Information Portal. (04.03.2012). High Turnout As Clear Evidence of Elections Legitimacy https://er.ru/activity/news/zheleznyak-vysokaya-yavka-ubeditelnoe-svidetelstvo-legitimnosti-vyborov_77179

³⁵ VEDOMOSTI.RU. (20.03.2016). Constitutional Court Decides That Military Contractors Can Vote During Municipal Elections <https://www.vedomosti.ru/politics/articles/2016/03/21/634342-voennosluzhaschie-kontraktniki-golosovat>

³⁶ RBC.RU. (22.03.2018). Electoral Sultanates – How Regions-Record Breakers Vote <https://www.rbc.ru/politics/22/03/2018/5ab0e12b9a79477b98c164cb>

Model 9 attempts to clarify this question by introducing the new dummy variable for electoral sultanates. These are 12 regions including in the North Caucasus (including Chechnya, Dagestan, Kabardian-Balkar and Carachaevo-Circassian republics), Kemero-vo and Tyva majority of which were found at the bottom of the governance ranking. Here, coefficient for sultanate dummy variable is statistically significant at the level of 0.05. It shows that on average in sultanate regions that presumably apply coercion to the higher extent than other regions, electoral outcome is 11.4% more favorable for the incumbent than in non-sultanate constituencies. However, this does not serve as sufficient evidence to support the coercion argument.

Model 10 evaluates impact of sultanate variable on election outcome while controlling for unemployment, average income, infant mortality and number of hospital beds. The idea behind this specification is to test whether level of economic activity and quality of public services may in principle affect voter's choice in sultanate regions. Coefficient for sultanate variable in this model retains its statistical properties. It is statistically significant at the level of 0.05. Controlling for other independent variables, however, does not change this coefficient significantly. Here, electoral outcome is 10.3% more favorable than in non-sultanate regions which is an insignificant decrease by 1.1% as compared to previous model. This finding may serve as evidence of coercion at least in 12 regions of Russia where local elites are more influential than economic and state capacity factors over voters' political choice. **Table 5** sums up results of regression analysis for Models 8-10.

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Photo by Phil Scroggs.

Table 4: Regression Outputs for Models 6-7

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>		
	% of votes for the incumbent in 2018		
	(8)	(9)	(10)
Turnout (% of population casting votes)	53.71** (4.56)		
“Sultanate” Variable (1 – coercion, 0 – no coercion)		11.46** (1.39)	10.31** (1.61)
Average Income per Capita (log function)			-4.43 (3.76)
Unemployment Rate (%)			-0.13 (0.18)
Infant Mortality Rate (%)			51.9 (36.0)
Hospital Beds (Number per 10 000 population)			-0.09** (0.04)
Y-intercept	39.24** (3.16)	74.36** (0.55)	91.81** (10.14)
Observations	83	83	83
R ²	0.63	0.45	0.68

*Notes: **p<0.05; ***p<0.01. Standard error in brackets*

This section provided valuable insights about electoral behavior and factors that influence it in distinct regional setting of Russia. First, by studying relations between election outcomes and economic and governance factors we revealed clientelist transactions. Although data and methods used are insufficient to explicitly identify client-patron relations on individual level, there is clear pattern of clientelism between regional authorities and central government. This finding corresponds well with historical developments in such regions as Chechnya and Tatarstan. Despite drastic economic and state capacity differences, both share heritage of fighting for their sovereignty. Today, however, both are electoral sultanates, providing unparalleled support for the incumbent. Then, we confirmed empirical evidence provided in the large body of scholar literature, depicting an inverse trend between state capacity and electoral choice. We contributed to this knowledge by examining the Russian voters’ behavior and learned that lower state capacity parameters positively affect political support for the regime. It means that Russian voters in general are skeptical about potential new regime’s capacity to deliver tangible results in economy and public administration. Additionally, we discovered that in a wide range of economic and state capacity variables, infant mortality rate and number of hospital beds remained fairly robust in our models, which goes in line with scholars who present these variables as a solid proxy for state capacity. At the same time, we were unable to clearly support or reject our initial hypothesis about political coercion. On the one hand, there is a body of unstructured qualitative data in the form reports by media and election observers which could not be properly operationalized for the purposes of our research. On the other hand, by introducing the sultanate variable we managed to identify coercion at least in 12 regions while controlling for economic and state capacity factors.

5. Conclusion

This paper examined factors that have shaped political landscape in Russia for 3 post-soviet decades on the example of presidential campaign in 2018. We discovered valuable insights about what matters and what does not for voters and the federal government when it comes to running a political campaign across highly differentiated regional settings of the world's largest country. Our findings may be summarized in 4 major points.

Firstly, cross-regional comparison of Russian regions confirmed scholar findings about the impact of state capacity factors on individual political choice. When it comes to elections in weak democracies, voters in principal are skeptical about government's capability and expertise to solve burning problems and social issues. In this environment they are prone to nurturing well-established relationships with patrons who may be representatives of local governments or connected businessmen other than to support politicians with programmatic agendas. Russian case confirms this. Infant mortality rate and number of hospital beds, proxies for state capacity, remained robust and statistically significant across the majority of regression models. Lower provision of public goods (healthcare) co-existed with higher political support for the incumbent.

Secondly, application of economic indicators provides evidence of their negative impact on political pro-government choices among voters. Although operationalization of our models did not provide robust and statistically significant coefficients, such variables as unemployment and average income per capita are insightful for future research. They suggest that higher unemployment and lower wage provide more political support for the incumbent. This goes in line with scholars who discovered how politicians choose to target poorer voters with upfront and small-scale material benefits, other than richer groups that require more "common good" programmatic policies.

Thirdly, we found out that clientelism takes place in Russia. However, its nature is different from individual client-patron relationships. The central government uses federal subsidies as one of its tools to ensure desired political goals. Our evidence suggests that the top-receivers of subsidies provide best political outcomes for the incumbent. This goes in line with poor state capacity and overall underdevelopment in such constituencies. However, such clientelism is atypical because it is subject to local (client)-central (patron) government relationships with little to no direct contact with individual voters.

Additionally, we identified symptoms of coercion during elections in Russia. Although no systematized data on coercion is available, we worked with so-called "electoral sultanates" – regions of Russia with the highest political turnout and support for the incumbent no matter their economic environment.

In our study we revealed that such regions, where local elites have more influence on political outcomes than quality of public sector and economic activity, high turnout and political support go hand-in-glove even after controlling for state capacity and economic factors. This serves as evidence of coercion, when voters are enforced to attend elections and cast their votes in favor of the incumbent.

Finally, our findings may be altogether summarized in the final conclusion. Description of Russia as a weak state is inaccurate. Weak states are incapable of ensuring desired political outcomes in regions that differ by economic wealth, quality of public sector and life in general, population size or distance to federal center. Therefore, we imply that the existing political system utilizes regional differences as a tool to secure its political interest when the time for elections comes.

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Photo by Arnaud Jaegers.

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APPENDIX

Annex A: Variables description

	Description	Source
Dependent Variable		
Y	% of voters in favor of incumbent	RBC.RU Elections 2018: Turnout and Results
Independent Variables		
X1	GRP 2018 in mln EUR (calculated from RUR at average annual exchange RUR/EUR rate for 2018)	ROSSTAT. Russian Statistical Bulletin 2020. System of National Accounts (R_13)
X2	logIncome per capita (calculated from RUR at average annual exchange RUR/EUR rate for 2018)	ROSSTAT. Russian Statistical Bulletin 2019. Living Standards (R_6)
X3	Industrial Output in mln EUR (calculated from RUR at average annual exchange RUR/EUR rate for 2018). For regions with little to now manufacturing figure for mining output was taken	ROSSTAT. Russian Statistical Bulletin 2019. Industrial Production (R_17)
X4	R'n'D Expenses in mln EUR (calculated from RUR at average annual exchange RUR/EUR rate for 2018)	ROSSTAT. Russian Statistical Bulletin 2019. Science and Innovations (R_23)
X5	% of unemployed	ROSSTAT. Russian Statistical Bulletin 2019. Labor (R_5)
X6	Federal Taxes Received in mln EUR (calculated from RUR at average annual exchange RUR/EUR rate for 2018)	Federal Tax Service. Federal Tax Receipts (as of 01.01.2019)
X7	% of infant mortality	ROSSTAT. Russian Statistical Bulletin 2019. Population (R_4)

X8	% of net migration	ROSSTAT. Russian Statistical Bulletin 2019. Population (R_4)
X9	% of exports in Gross Regional Product in mln EUR (calculated from RUR at average annual exchange RUR/EUR rate for 2018)	ROSSTAT. Russian Statistical Bulletin 2019. Foreign Trade (R_26)
X10	Cargo transported by roads in mln tons	ROSSTAT. Russian Statistical Bulletin 2019. Transport (R_21)
X11	Number of hospital beds per 10000 population	ROSSTAT. Russian Statistical Bulletin 2019. Public Health (R_8)
X12	Clientelism Proxy. Dummy-variable (0,1) for 4 subsidy groups (1 – no subsidies, 2 – subsidized up to 10%, 3 – subsidized by 10-40%, 4 – heavily subsidized by more than 40%)	Budget.gov.ru Subsidy Dependence of Russian Regions
X13	Coercion Proxy. Dummy-variable (0,1) for sultanate regions	RBC.RU. Electoral Sultanates – How Regions-Record Breakers Vote

Four datasets (Economy, Capacity, Elections, Region Score) and OLS regression models (*.xlsx) are available on Google Drive via download link:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1UtH-wdAz0xFG-X3_w4prs8ozl94g16LOF/view?usp=sharing

Password: **098022**

Annex B: Subnational Russia: Good governance rank 2018

#	Region	Combined Score	Economy Score	State Capacity Score
1	The City of Saint-Petersburg	87,7	95,5	79,8
2	The City of Moscow	83,0	98,5	67,4
3	Tyumen region	82,9	91,8	74
4	Moscow region	82,4	95,2	69,6
5	Republic of Tatarstan	81,9	90,8	73
6	Khanty-Mansi autonomous area - Yugra	81,5	87,8	75,2
7	Sverdlovsk region	81,2	86,7	75,8
8	Leningrad region	79,3	81,3	77,2
9	Krasnodar territory	77,3	79,8	74,8
10	Samara region	77,2	85,3	69
11	Krasnoyarsk territory	76,0	84,2	67,8
12	Rostov region	74,5	77,2	71,8
13	Sakhalin region	74,5	66,3	82,6
14	Voronezh region	72,1	76,7	67,6
15	Nizhny novgorod region	71,9	78,2	65,6
16	Republic of Bashkortastan	71,7	81,3	62
17	Primorsky territory	71,1	72,0	70,2
18	Novosibirsk region	71,1	71,5	70,6
19	Lipetsk region	70,8	64,5	77
20	Tula region	69,6	70,5	68,6
21	Belgorod region	69,4	73,3	65,4
22	Republic of Sakha (Yakutia)	68,9	71,3	66,4
23	Yaroslavl region	68,5	63,0	74
24	Irkutsk region	67,3	66,8	67,8
25	Kemerovo region	66,2	59,5	72,8

26	Kaliningrad region	66,1	63,2	69
27	Kaluga region	65,3	72,7	58
28	Tomsk region	65,1	62,7	67,6
29	Yamalo-Nenets autonomous area	64,4	80,3	48,4
30	Orenburg region	63,3	68,5	58
31	Perm region	63,2	71,5	54,8
32	Khabarovsk territory	62,6	59,7	65,6
33	Volgograd region	62,1	63,2	61
34	Saratov region	61,5	61,7	61,4
35	Republic of Komi	60,8	60,8	60,8
36	Penza region	60,1	56,3	63,8
37	Kursk region	59,7	60,3	59
38	Vologda region	59,7	58,5	60,8
39	Arkhangelsk region	59,6	60,7	58,6
40	Tver region	59,3	60,8	57,8
41	Udmurt Republic	58,7	63,7	53,8
42	Bryansk region	58,4	56,3	60,4
43	Novgorod region	58,0	51,0	65
44	Amur region	58,0	51,5	64,4
45	Ryazan region	57,3	60,7	54
46	Magadan region	57,3	56,2	58,4
47	Stavropol territory	57,2	58,5	55,8
48	Ulyanovsk region	56,9	61,3	52,4
49	Smolensk region	56,8	51,5	62
50	Vladimir region	56,5	60,3	52,6
51	Murmansk region	55,8	57,7	54
52	Kirov region	55,7	54,2	57,2
53	Republic of Altai	54,1	74,0	34,2
54	Altai territory	53,4	51,8	55

55	Omsk region	53,1	65,3	40,8
56	Tambov region	51,3	51,5	51
57	Chukotka autonomous area	51,0	47,3	54,6
58	Republic of Mordovia	49,2	44,2	54,2
59	Ivanovo region	48,6	46,2	51
60	Nenets autonomous area	48,5	52,5	44,4
61	Kamchatka region	48,4	46,8	50
62	Republic of Karelia	47,7	43,5	51,8
63	Oryol region	47,3	43,2	51,4
64	Astrakhan region	47,1	48,5	45,6
65	Republic of Khakassia	47,0	33,8	60,2
66	Chuvash Republic	46,9	46,5	47,2
67	Republic of Adygeya	44,7	34,2	55,2
68	Kostroma region	44,6	40,3	48,8
69	Pskov region	44,5	33,7	55,4
70	Zabaikalskiy territory	44,0	39,7	48,4
71	Republic of Buryatia	43,9	36,2	51,6
72	Republic of Mariy El	43,7	35,0	52,4
73	Chelyabinsk region	37,8	20,3	55,2
74	Republic of Tyva	37,4	20,5	54,2
75	Republic of Daghestan	37,2	43,2	31,2
76	Republic of North Ossetia -Alania	36,7	27,5	45,8
77	Jewish autonomous region	35,9	26,5	45,2
78	Kurgan region	34,9	31,5	38,2
79	Kabardian-Balkar Republic	31,7	27,5	35,8
80	Chechen Republic	30,1	26,5	33,6
81	Republic of Ingushetia	27,6	18,3	36,8
82	Karachaev-Circassian Republic	26,1	24,0	28,2
83	Republic of Kalmykia	23,6	21,2	26

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